

REALISE: pRoduce Actionable poLicy Insights that enable a sound balance between Security and opEnness of the EU research and innovation ecosystems

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Abstract	This Deliverable provides a data management plan for the REALISE project, to be applied to the datasets generated in the context of research and technology transfer activities. It identifies the main data to be collected, generated and manipulated within the project, outlining the management of the datasets and which of them will be openly shared. This document represents a preliminary plan. It will be further detailed and updated if needed, in line with the activities of the project.
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¹ The labels used mean: Public — fully open (automatically posted online); Sensitive — limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement; EU classified — RESTREINT-UE/EU-RESTRICTED, CONFIDENTIEL-UE/EU-CONFIDENTIAL, SECRET-UE/EU-SECRET under Decision 2015/444.

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1. Introduction and Document Structure

This Data Management Plan (DMP) outlines the data lifecycle, storage, and sharing strategies for the project, in strict compliance with Horizon Europe Open Science requirements and the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable). This DMP is conceived as a “living document”. The current version represents the initial strategy established at the beginning of the project. It will be periodically reviewed and formally updated throughout the project’s lifecycle to reflect any operational changes, newly adopted tools (e.g., institutional Data Governance platforms), or refined methodologies.

The document is structured according to the standard European Commission DMP template. For clarity and to facilitate the evaluation process, the original template questions and guiding prompts have been retained and highlighted in green throughout the text. The specific project strategies, actions, and responses provided by the Fellow are detailed immediately below each green prompt.

2. REALISE project in a nutshell

European and global Research and Innovation Ecosystems (RIEs) are at risk. Planetary tensions have exposed EU vulnerabilities and elevated technology sovereignty to the top of policy agendas. Open RIEs are now contested spaces increasingly being viewed through the lens of protectionism, jeopardizing science as a universal and public good essential for addressing global challenges.

Achieving a sound balance between security and openness (S&O) is imperative. To date, however, the lack of scientific evidence prevents us from holistically addressing how technological sovereignty is affecting both the operations of RIEs and the geography of innovation, while the research community struggles with adoption and implementation of fragmented and often impractical guidance.

Using the semiconductor industry as a testbed, the Fellowship combines deep theoretical grounding with a strong applied focus. Based on an interdisciplinary multi-methodological approach, the Overall Objective is to produce Actionable Policy Insights that enable a sound balance between Security and openness (REALISE) in EU RIEs.

More specifically, REALISE targets two Specific Objectives (SOs):

- **SO1: To break new ground in the current European and global scholarly understanding of technological sovereignty and its impact on RIEs (WP1).** REALISE applies a theoretical framework developed in International Political Economy (IPE) to assess government interventions in high technology sectors and uses it in a novel and enriched context to study dynamics pertinent to research policy and higher education studies. This allows using IPE lens to cast light on the processes and consequences of technological sovereignty and evaluate its impact on RIEs’ global operations and exchanges.
- **SO2: To enable the effective balancing of S&O in RIEs at the EU supranational level, by developing tools to upskill RIEs current and future researchers and research managers (RMs) (WP2).** By systemizing the fragmentation of existing guidelines on research security, REALISE develops 2 key tools: 1) a state-of-the-art

vademecum providing researchers with an operational instrument; 2) an avant-garde S&O protocol for capacity-building of RMs.

REALISE’s tridimensional impact is intertwined with the pursuit of a holistic approach that advances world-class knowledge and develops governance mechanisms for balancing S&O in RIEs. This approach, developed with contributions from relevant stakeholders – including the private sector – aims to be responsive to real needs, turning RIEs from existing pockets of excellence into thriving ecosystems.

Training at prestigious academic institutions in the US and EU, along with the placement at INSIDE (a leading Industry Association focused on Intelligent Digital Systems), will equip the researcher with amplified and cross-cutting skills to become a hybrid investigator to both steer scientific research in academia and support STI domains of policy-making for industrial organizations and institutional settings, while facilitating the dialogue between different actors of the EU RIEs.

3. Data Summary

Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.

What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?

What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?

What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?

What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?

To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?

The project will both generate new data and re-use existing data.

2.1 Generated data and outputs:

NAME OF RESOURCE	TYPE OF RESOURCE (i.e. database, interview etc)	TYPE OF ACCESS (i.e. free, subscription etc)	URL	PURPOSE	LICENSE	EXPECTED SIZE (MB/GB/TB/etc)
Article 1	Scientific Publication	Open	https://zenodo.org/communities/realise_community/records	Generate new knowledge	CC BY 4.0	< 3MB
Article 2	Scientific Publication	Open	https://zenodo.org/communities/rea	Generate new knowledge	CC BY 4.0	< 3MB

			lise_community/records			
Vademecum	Guidelines	Open	https://zenodo.org/communities/realise_community/records	Capacity-building	CC BY 4.0	< 10MB
Protocol	Guidelines	Open	https://zenodo.org/communities/realise_community/records	Capacity-building	CC BY 4.0	< 10MB
Policy paper	Policy suggestions	Open	https://zenodo.org/communities/realise_community/records	To influence policy development.	CC BY 4.0	< 3MB
Literature Review Dataset/Matrix	Bibliographic Dataset (Excel/RIS)	Open	https://zenodo.org/communities/realise_community/records	To allow other researchers to access the comprehensive list of sources and categorization used for the state-of-the-art analysis.	CC BY 4.0	< 5 MB
Anonymized Survey Data	Tabular Data (.csv)	Open	https://zenodo.org/communities/realise_community/records	To allow statistical validation of the project's results and reuse of the dataset for secondary analysis.	CC BY 4.0	< 5 MB
Raw Survey Data (Personal)	Tabular Data	Closed (Confidential)	N/A (Stored locally/secure server)	Contains personal identifiers (if any) or metadata not suitable for	N/A	< 5 MB

				public release due to GDPR. Used for internal verification only.		
Anonymized Focus Group Transcripts	Text Documents (.pdf/.txt)	Open	https://zenodo.org/communities/realise_community/records	To provide qualitative evidence supporting the research findings, ensuring transparency while protecting participants' anonymity.	Anonymized Focus Group Transcripts	< 5 MB
Raw Focus Group Recordings	Audio/Video Files (.mp3/.mp4)	Closed (Confidential)	N/A (Stored locally/secure server)	Original recordings used for transcription. Kept closed to protect participants' voice and identity (GDPR).	N/A	~ 2 GB

(Tab. 1)

2.2 Reused data:

NAME OF RESOURCE	TYPE OF RESOURCE (i.e. database, interview etc)	TYPE OF ACCESS (i.e. free, subscription etc)	URL	PURPOSE	LICENSE	EXPECTED SIZE (MB/GB/TB/etc)
Scopus (Elsevier)	Bibliographic Database	Subscription (via Host Institution)	https://www.elsevier.com/products/scopus	Main source for the literature review dataset/matrix, bibliometric analysis, and citation tracking.	Subject to original subscription license (Right to access/read)	< 100 MB (Metadata and abstracts export)

Academic Publisher Databases (e.g., Wiley, EconLit, JSTOR)	Full-text Databases	Subscription (via Host/Secondment Inst.)	Various (e.g., onlinelibrary.wiley.com)	Access to full-text academic articles for qualitative analysis and state-of-the-art review.	Subject to original subscription license (Right to access/read)	< 500 MB (Cumulative PDFs)
Google Scholar	Academic Search Engine	Free	https://scholar.google.com/	Preliminary literature scoping and cross-verification of citations.	N/A (Public Search Engine)	< 10 MB (Citation data/BibTeX exports)
OECD's Research Security Portal	Database	Free	https://stip.oecd.org/stip/research-security-portal	To collect policy initiatives to safeguard national and economic security in public research enacted by multiple actors in the international research ecosystem.	CC BY 4.0	189Kb
EC-OECD STIP Compass database of STI policies	Various Databases	Free	https://stip.oecd.org/stip/	To access qualitative and quantitative data on national trends in science, technology and innovation (STI) policy together in one place.	CC BY 4.0	58Kb
Library of Congress (US)	Various act and legislations	Free	https://www.congress.gov/	The largest library in the world and serves as the main research arm of the US Congress and the national library of the US. It houses over 170 million items, including books, manuscripts, recordings, and photos, providing	Varying rights and access restrictions	< 5MB (per doc)

				research services to Congress and the public.		
EUR-Lex (European Union)	Legislation and Case Law Database	Free	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/	The official gateway to EU Law, providing access to the Official Journal, Treaties, legal acts, case-law, and legislative procedures.	CC BY 4.0 (Reuse authorised)	< 5MB (per doc)
Légifrance (France)	National Legislation Database	Free	https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/	The official portal to French law, containing the Constitution, codes, laws, decrees, and collective agreements.	Open Licence (Etalab)	< 5MB (per doc)
Gesetze im Internet (Germany)	Federal Legislation Database	Free	https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/	The official platform provided by the Federal Ministry of Justice, hosting nearly all current federal laws and regulations.	Public Domain (Official Works)	< 2MB (per doc)
Wetten.nl/Overheid.nl (Netherlands)	Consolidated Legislation	Free	https://wetten.overheid.nl/	The central access point for all Dutch government information, containing the consolidated texts of all current legislation.	CC0 1.0 (Public Domain)	< 2MB (per doc)
Laws and Regulations Database of the ROC (Taiwan)	National Legislation Database	Free	https://law.moj.gov.tw/Eng/	The official database maintained by the Ministry of Justice, providing English translations and original texts of Taiwan's laws.	Government Open Data (Open License)	< 2MB (per doc)
National Database of Laws and Regulations (China)	National Legislation Database	Free	https://flk.npc.gov.cn/	The official database of the National People's Congress, covering all laws, administrative regulations, and	Public Domain (Official Works)	< 5MB (per doc)

				judicial interpretations.		
Korean Law Information Center (South Korea)	National Legislation Database	Free	https://www.law.go.kr/LSW/eng/	The official legal information service operated by the Ministry of Government Legislation, providing English translations of Korean acts.	Korea Open Government License	< 3MB (per doc)
Japanese Law Translation / e-Gov (Japan)	Legislation Database	Free	https://www.japaneselawtranslation.go.jp/	The official Ministry of Justice database for Japanese laws and their English translations. (Native text at elaws.e-gov.go.jp).	Government of Japan Standard Terms (Open)	< 2MB (per doc)

(Tab.2)

At this stage, the volume of data collected/generated is approximately estimated at less than 30 GB.

To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?

Outside this project, the datasets might be useful to:

- scientific community working in the fields of political economy, research policy, and higher education studies;
- STI and research security policy-makers;
- public entities operating in the field of STI policies;
- private entities operating in the field of research.

Whenever possible, open, non-proprietary formats commonly used by the research community for the project data, will be used throughout the research process, as summarized in the following table:

TYPE OF DATA	PREFERRED FILE FORMAT(S)	OTHER ACCEPTABLE FORMAT(S)	EXPECTED SIZE
A. Textual	Rich Text Format (.rtf) plain text, ASCII (.txt) Adobe Portable Document Format (PDF/A, PDF) (.pdf)	Hypertext Mark-up Language (.html) MS Word (.doc/.docx)	700 MB

B. Images	TIFF 6.0 not compressed (.tif)	JPEG (.jpeg, .jpg, .jp2) GIF (.gif) TIFF (.tif, .tiff) RAW image format (.raw) BMP (.bmp)	100 MB
C. Video	MP4 (MPEG-4)	/	2.5 GB
D. Tabular Data/Codes	.csv	Open	< 1 MB
E. Scripts/Source Code	.py	Open	< 1 MB
F. Project Interchange Format	.xml	Open	< 5 MB

4. FAIR data

In order to make data findable, the following steps will be taken.

3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?

Project data and outputs will be deposited in the trusted repository Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/>) to ensure findability and long-term preservation. To further ensure discoverability, a dedicated project community named “REALISE Community” (https://zenodo.org/communities/realise_community) has been created in Zenodo to group all project-related data and outputs.

Each upload in Zenodo will be assigned a persistent identifier (DOI). Zenodo also supports DOI versioning, enabling precise citation and tracking of changes over time.

Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.

Rich metadata will be provided and include at least information on:

- Datasets;
- Funding and grant number;
- Licensing terms;
- Persistent identifiers;
- Authors and their affiliation;
- Links to related publications/works (if applicable).

Zenodo exposes metadata in recognized standard formats, including DataCite and Dublin Core, ensuring machine actionability and FAIRness (<https://about.zenodo.org/policies/>, sec. Content). In compliance with the Grant Agreement, all metadata deposited will be open access under a Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC0) license. This

ensures that information about the data remains publicly available and machine-actionable, even in cases where the datasets themselves must remain closed or restricted due to ethical or security obligations.

Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?

In order to increase the findability of each dataset and its reuse, once uploaded to Zenodo, the search keywords will be provided. Keywords will be aligned with the EuroVoc vocabulary, where possible, to ensure consistency and enhance findability”

The main keywords will be:

- Research Security
- New Economic Statecraft
- Tech War
- Semiconductors
- Research and Innovation Ecosystems (RIEs)
- Geopolitics
- Competitiveness, innovation, research and development
- EU research policy/Research policies in the EU
- Innovation management
- Political economy, institutional economics, law and economics
- Sovereignty, Globalisation, Economics of Innovation.

The list of keywords will be promptly modified as circumstances arise.

Additionally, the datasets will be indexed according to the JEL Classification System to facilitate categorization within the economic literature. The selected codes include:

JEL Code	Description
F52	National Security; Economic Nationalism
L50	Regulation and Industrial Policy (General)
O38	Government Policy for Innovation and R&D
L63	Electronics, Computers, and Communications Industry
O32	Management of Technological Innovation and R&D

The list of JEL codes too will be promptly modified as circumstances arise.

Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?

Zenodo allows harvesting and indexing of metadata. Harvesting is guaranteed by the OAI-PMH protocol (<https://about.zenodo.org/policies>, sec. “Access and reuse”), while indexing is supported and enhanced by the use of metadata standard (see above)”.

In addition, in order to increase data findability, naming conventions will be used. The naming convention for each dataset will be as follows: “DSx_REALISE_title_Vy”.

It must contain the following elements:

1. DS (short name for dataset) – followed by a unique chronological number of the project dataset, replacing x;
2. REALISE – name of the project;
3. title – indicates the title of the dataset;
4. V – indicates the version number, replacing y.

In order to increase findability, the folders will be organized as follows:

REALISE PROJECT

01 - Official documents

02 - Research data

- 002.1_raw data
- 002.2_bibliography
- 002.3_research design
- 002.4_generated databases

03 - Outputs

- 003.1_drafts
- 003.2_finalized files

04 - Outreach materials

- 004.1_Photos
- 004.2_Videos
- 004.3_...

3.2 Making data accessible

Repository:

Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?

The data will be deposited in Zenodo, which ensures compliance with the FAIR principles in data management:

<https://about.zenodo.org/policies>;
<https://about.zenodo.org/infrastructure>.

Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?

Zenodo offers free data storage up to 50 GB per record. Higher quotas can be requested and granted on a case-by-case basis, although it is not currently foreseen.

Due to the small size of data generated by the project, no agreements have been made with the repository up until now. Appropriate arrangements with the repository will be discussed if needed.

Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?

Zenodo allows for the assignment of both a versioned DOI and the updating if needed (<https://about.zenodo.org/principles>, section “Fair principles”).

Data:

Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.

Data will be archived on Zenodo as soon as possible, at the latest at the time of publication of the related scientific publication. The project data will follow the principle “as open as possible, as closed as necessary”, therefore they will be open unless ethical, confidentiality, security or privacy restrictions apply.

In line with the “as open as possible, as closed as necessary” principle, the REALISE project will maximize open access to research data while strictly adhering to ethical guidelines and GDPR regulations regarding the protection of personal data.

1. Data made Openly Available (Anonymized): the following datasets will be made openly available on Zenodo (CC BY 4.0) to ensure transparency and reproducibility:

1. Literature review dataset/matrix: contains bibliographic references and categorization tags. No personal data involved.
2. Research design and methodological Roadmap: a comprehensive document containing the roadmap of the research process for each output outlined (e.g., Scientific articles, Vademecum, Protocol), including the associated resources and specific methodology applied. Sharing this documentation is crucial to validate the scientific workflow and allow external replication of the study design.
3. Pre-prints of scientific publications: to foster early sharing and ensure immediate access to findings without waiting for publisher delays, pre-prints (submitted versions) of all scientific articles will be deposited in Zenodo (CC BY 4.0) parallel to journal submission.
4. Open access to peer-reviewed scientific publications: in strict compliance with Grant Agreement Art. 17, immediate open access to the peer-reviewed content will be ensured. At the latest at the time of publication, a machine-readable copy of the Author Accepted Manuscript (AAM) or the Version of Record (VoR) will be deposited in Zenodo under a CC BY 4.0 license. Beneficiaries will retain sufficient intellectual property rights to comply with these open access requirements.
5. Anonymized survey data: the tabular dataset resulting from the survey will be shared only after a rigorous process of anonymization (see Data Security Section). All direct identifiers (names, emails) and indirect identifiers (IP addresses, specific job titles that could lead to re-identification) will be removed or aggregated.
6. Anonymized Focus Group transcripts: transcripts will be edited to remove names and specific institutional references that could reveal the identity of the participants. If full anonymization compromises the scientific value, aggregated thematic reports will be shared instead (see Data Security Section).
7. Source code and scripts: all .py scripts and ATLAS.ti export files (.xml) used for analysis will be open.

2. Data kept Closed/Restricted (Confidential): certain datasets will not be shared publicly due to legal (GDPR) and ethical constraints:

1. Raw survey Data: the original dataset containing timestamps, IP addresses, and contact details (collected for follow-up purposes) will be kept closed and stored securely in the UNIMC's institutional Data Governance Platform ClaryData, with access limited to the researcher.
2. Raw audio/video recordings: recordings of Focus Groups constitute biometric data and will be kept strictly confidential and stored securely in the UNIMC's institutional Data Governance Platform ClaryData. They are used solely for transcription/analysis by the researcher and will not be published to protect participants' privacy and reputation.
3. Informed Consent forms: signed forms containing names and signatures will be stored separately from the research data and kept closed.

3. Anonymization and Pseudonymization Strategy: to manage the transition from closed to open data, the project adopts a pseudonymization strategy during the active research phase:

1. Direct identifiers are replaced by a code (e.g., Participant_01).
2. The "key" linking the code to the identity is stored securely and separately from the research data (in a password-protected offline folder).
3. For the final publication (Open Data), the data is fully anonymized, meaning the key is destroyed or permanently separated, making re-identification impossible.

In any case, metadata will remain openly available under CC0, while access to related data may be restricted or authorized upon justified request, in compliance with GDPR and the Grant Agreement.

If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.

No embargo is currently foreseen at this time.

Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?

Data and metadata are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol, which is open, free, and universally implementable. Metadata are harvestable using the OAI-PMH protocol by the record identifier and the collection name. Metadata are also retrievable through the public REST API. OAI-PMH and REST are open, free and universal protocols for information retrieval on the web (<https://about.zenodo.org/policies>, section "Access and reuse").

If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?

Access to restricted data (specifically: raw audio recordings, raw survey data containing identifiers, and signed informed consent forms) will be strictly limited to the MSCA Fellow.

Scientific Supervisors may be granted access for validation purposes only.

- During the project: as already detailed in the Data Security section, raw data containing personal identifiers will be stored exclusively on the Host Institution's secure storage infrastructure (e.g., the institutional Data Governance Platform or authorized secure drives), accessible only via authentication.
- After the project: restricted data will not be made publicly accessible. It will be securely archived for a period of 5 years (or as per institutional policy) solely for verification purposes in case of scientific misconduct allegations or audits, after which it will be permanently deleted. No external access will be provided to raw personal data.

How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?

Since restricted data (e.g., raw recordings, personal data) are NOT stored on public repositories like Zenodo but solely on the Host Institution's secure internal storage, the identity of the person accessing them is ascertained through the University's IT authentication system. Access to the secure storage requires personal institutional credentials (username/password) and is protected by firewalls. This ensures that only the authorized MSCA Fellow (and Supervisors, if strictly necessary) can physically access the files, preventing unauthorized internal or external access.

Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?

The establishment of a separate formal data access committee is not considered necessary for a project of this scale. However, the governance of restricted data is supported by the advisory role of the Host Institution's Data Protection Officer (DPO). Any exceptional request for access to restricted data (e.g., for legal reasons or ethical audits) will be assessed by the MSCA Fellow in strict coordination with the DPO and the Ethics Committee, ensuring full compliance with GDPR and the initial consent provided by participants.

Metadata:

Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CCO, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?

Metadata of deposited data will be always openly available and freely reusable under the CC 0.0 license, as per the Grant Agreement.

Metadata will be in line with the FAIR principles (machine-actionable in particular) and will provide information at least about the following:

1. datasets (description, date of deposit, author(s), venue and embargo);
2. Horizon Europe funding and grant number;
3. grant project name, acronym and number;
4. licensing terms;
5. persistent identifiers for the dataset;
6. authors and their affiliation.

When applicable, the metadata will include persistent identifiers for related publications and other research outputs.

Information about the accessibility of the dataset is also included in the metadata.

How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?

Data and metadata will remain available and findable for the lifetime of the repository, currently guaranteed for the next 20 years at least. According to Zenodo policy, metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available.

Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

Currently, it is not expected that any specific software or tools will be needed to access and use the data. Data will be made available in widely used, open and interoperable formats, ensuring long-term accessibility. Part of the analysis will be conducted using ATLAS.ti®, a proprietary data analysis software. However, files generated through ATLAS.ti® will be exported and converted into open non-proprietary formats prior to deposit in Zenodo, thus ensuring that access does not depend on the use of a proprietary software or license. Any additional technical needs that may emerge will be assessed during the project and the DMP will be updated accordingly if necessary.

3.2 Making data interoperable

What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?

In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining or extending them?

Will your data include qualified references² to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?

Technical interoperability – Formats and Standards

To ensure technical interoperability and allow for seamless data exchange across different systems and disciplines, the project will strictly adhere to widely used, non-proprietary standard file formats, directly mapping the resources listed in Table 1.

By avoiding proprietary formats where possible, the project ensures that the methodological process remains reproducible for external validation. The specific formats to be used include:

² A qualified reference is a cross-reference that explains its intent. For example, X is regulator of Y is a much more qualified reference than X is associated with Y, or X see also Y. The goal therefore is to create as many meaningful links as possible between (meta)data resources to enrich the contextual knowledge about the data. (Source: <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/i3-metadata-include-qualified-references-metadata/>)

- Scientific Publications and Guidelines: all textual outputs listed in Table 1 (i.e., Scientific Articles, Vademecum, Protocol, Policy Paper) will be made available in PDF/A (Portable Document Format for Archiving) to ensure long-term preservation and accessibility across all operating systems. Editable versions (DOCX) may be provided where community feedback is encouraged.
- Bibliographic Datasets: the Literature Review Dataset/Matrix will be exported in standard bibliographic formats such as .RIS or .BIB (BibTeX). This ensures full interoperability with all major reference management software (e.g., Zotero, Mendeley, EndNote), allowing other researchers to easily reuse the citation list.
- Tabular Survey Data: both the Anonymized Survey Data and the internal Raw Survey Data will be stored in .CSV (Comma-Separated Values) format. This plain-text format ensures that data generated in software such as ATLAS.ti® can be imported into any statistical software (R, Python, SPSS, Excel) and accessed as well as re-used by researchers without compatibility barriers.
- Qualitative Data (Transcripts and Audio):
 - Anonymized Focus Group transcripts will be saved as .TXT or .PDF files to ensure they are human-readable and compatible with qualitative analysis software (e.g., NVivo, ATLAS.ti).
 - Raw Focus Group recordings (restricted) will be stored in standard open media formats (MP3 for audio, MP4 for video) to ensure playback on standard media players without requiring proprietary codecs.
- Code and scripts: scripts used for analysis will be saved as .py (Python) files. These text-based files are universally readable and executable in standard environments such as Visual Studio Code, ensuring the transparency of the analytical process.
- Text and literature: literature reviews and reports will be maintained in PDF and .docx formats to ensure accessibility across all standard word processors and operating systems.
- Media: photos and recordings of Open Science (OS) research practices (collected under participant consent) will be stored in standard JPEG and MP4 formats, ensuring they are viewable on any standard media player.

Semantic interoperability – Vocabularies and Documentation

To ensure semantic interoperability – meaning that the data can be correctly interpreted by researchers from other disciplines – the dataset will be accompanied by comprehensive documentation (e.g., README files) describing the variable structures and codes.

Furthermore, a standard vocabulary will be used for all data types to enable cross-disciplinary understanding. The specific vocabularies and ontological references that will guide the data definition include:

- *The Routledge Encyclopedia of International Political Economy* (Jones)
<https://www.routledge.com/Routledge-Encyclopedia-of-International-Political-Economy/Jones/p/book/9780203440162>.
- *The New Palgrave Dictionary of Economics* (Springer)
<https://link.springer.com/referencework/10.1057/978-1-349-95121-5>.
- *The Oxford Handbook of Industrial Policy* (OUP)
<https://academic.oup.com/edited-volume/34292>.

In case of data coming from external sources, the deposited (meta)data will include

qualified references to these. Such references will include full details, including, where available, the related persistent identifiers, ensuring traceability and interoperability. Relationships between datasets will be clearly stated in the metadata (e.g. “is derived from/is referenced by, etc.)

3.3 Increase data re-use

How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?

The data will be documented appropriately to support interpretation, reuse and operability across disciplines, if necessary.

The Fellow will constantly document workflow throughout the project via readme files and/or a handbook, if necessary to facilitate understanding, which will be uploaded on Zenodo.

Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?

Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?

The data will be archived on Zenodo and will be made available for re-use with the appropriate license.

Whenever possible, the license proposed will be Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0) which allows third parties to share and adapt the data without restriction as long as attribution is provided (see table in Section 1).

To further increase data reuse, and in addition to the measures described under findability, accessibility and interoperability, README files will be provided where relevant. These will describe the methodology of data collection, data cleaning and analysis procedures. This documentation will support the reproducibility of results and facilitate the reuse of data.

Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.

Data quality will be ensured throughout the research lifecycle through the following rigorous procedures:

- Methodological pre-registration: To prevent bias and ensure transparency, the survey methodology and hypotheses will be pre-registered (e.g., on OSF or Zenodo) prior to the launch of data collection.
- Transcription quality check: Transcriptions of Focus Groups (performed via software tools) will undergo a mandatory manual double-check by the Fellow against the original audio recordings to ensure verbatim accuracy and correct attribution of speakers before coding.
- Data cleaning: quantitative survey data will be processed using Python scripts (as

detailed in Sec. 2.3) to perform data cleaning, such as detecting outliers, consistency checks, and removing incomplete entries/duplicates before statistical analysis.

- AI: as mentioned, AI-assisted coding in ATLAS.ti will be subjected to human validation. The Fellow will verify every AI-generated code to ensure it aligns with the theoretical framework and context.
- Anonymization protocol: survey data containing personal information processed using the institutional Data Governance Platform to ensure standardized and irreversible anonymization. In the interim, strict separation between keys and pseudo-anonymized data is maintained to ensure the integrity of the dataset.
- Traceability: the Fellow will always provide accurate references to the sources used, enabling external users to validate the results.
- Supervisory review: as a final quality gate, the Scientific Supervisors (Beneficiary and Host) will revise the drafts of all deliverables and datasets before publication or deposit.

Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects.

5. Other research outputs

In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.).

Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles.

In addition to the datasets described in the previous sections, the project will generate, preserve, and share the following non-data research outputs to ensure full reproducibility and maximize impact:

- Methodological instruments: the full text of the Survey Questionnaire (blank model) and the Focus Group Topic Guide/Protocol. Sharing these tools allows other researchers to replicate the study design.
- Software/code: The Python scripts (.py) and ATLAS.ti XML schemas developed for data cleaning and analysis.
- Dissemination materials: Conference presentations (slides), posters, and other visual materials used to disseminate results at scientific events.

All these outputs will be deposited in Zenodo alongside the datasets. They will be assigned a specific DOI, described with rich metadata, and shared under an open license (CC BY 4.0) and open standard formats to guarantee compliance with FAIR principles. Specifically for the software scripts, if the code development becomes substantial, a repository on GitHub

will be created and linked to Zenodo to enable the assignment of a DOI, ensure version control, software citation, and long-term preservation.

6. Allocation of resources

What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.) ?

How will these be covered? Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part of the Horizon Europe grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions)

Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

How will long term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?

Data management costs are included in the general management of the project and no additional costs are foreseen at this stage.

The institutional Data Governance platform Clarydata is owned by the University of Macerata and does not entail direct costs for the REALISE project.

The selected repository, Zenodo, offers free data storage up to 50 GB per record. Higher storage quotas can be requested and granted on a case-by-case basis; however, at this stage no additional storage needs beyond the standard quota are currently foreseen for the REALISE project. UNIMC will discuss appropriate arrangements with the repository if needed.

The Fellow will be responsible for data collection, metadata production, data quality, storage, data archiving and data sharing.

The UNIMC Data Steward will give advice on FAIR related issues and will support in the drafting and updating of the Data Management Plan.

Due to the small size of data generated by the project, at the moment no agreements have been made with the repository. UNIMC will discuss appropriate arrangements with the repository if needed.

7. Data security

What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?

Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?

All data generated, collected, or processed during the project will be stored, managed, and preserved in a secure manner, following the data protection, cybersecurity, and research integrity policies of UNIMC and the guidelines of Horizon Europe and MSCA.

Following a risk-based approach, non-personal research data will be stored and managed using the UNIMC institutional OneDrive service, which offers secure cloud storage, institutional authentication, and regular backup procedures.

Personal data and datasets requiring enhanced protection will be stored exclusively on the UNIMC institutional Data Governance platform Clarydata, a secure infrastructure designed to support research data lifecycle management that ensures compliance with GDPR and institutional data protection policies.

The platform provides:

- Controlled access through authentication;
- Role-based permissions to ensure that only authorised project staff can access, modify, or download the data;
- Data minimisation tool (anonymisation/pseudonymisation);
- Regular backup.

Depending on the sensitivity level of each dataset:

- Access will be restricted to authorised staff only;
- Sensitive data are not foreseen at this stage, but in any case, personal or confidential data will be stored in a secure, access-restricted area of the platform;
- Personal data will be pseudonymised or anonymised using the specific tool of the abovementioned secure platform.

The Fellow defines authorised users and the system administrator implements role-based permissions at platform level through authenticated access control. Authentication-based access control and role-based authorisation ensure that only approved users can view, modify, and/or download the data.

At project completion, original data containing personal or confidential information will remain stored in the university's secure platform. This data will be securely archived for a period of 5 years (or as per institutional policy) solely for verification purposes in case of scientific misconduct allegations or audits, after which it will be permanently deleted.

Data selected for long-term preservation and sharing will be deposited in the FAIR-compliant repository Zenodo, with no personal or sensitive information. Only anonymized data will be openly available on Zenodo, in order to protect participants' identity.

The chosen repository, Zenodo, is a repository that ensures long-term preservation of research data and outputs, at least for the duration of the same, currently guaranteed for at least the next 20 years.

Before being deposited on Zenodo, the data will be stored on the institutional One Drive of the University of Macerata, with regular backup.

8. Ethics

Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).

Will informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

Based on an internal screening and check, supported by experienced staff from the UniMC's Grant Office, the objectives, methodology, and results do not involve sensitive aspects related to the ethical dimension of research. No vulnerable populations, clinical

trials, or participation of children are foreseen. The research's focus on semiconductor research and innovation ecosystems does not raise ethical concerns.

In WP1 and WP2, co-productive forms of research like participative workshops and focus groups will be employed. A total of 50 participants – 25 from the U.S. (selected from the Berkeley Asia Pacific Economic Corridor Study Center (BASC), the Berkeley Risk and Security Lab (BRSL) at the University of California, Berkeley) and 25 from the Netherlands (selected from the Department of Political Science, VIDI Grant research community, and associated networks at Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam) – will participate on a voluntary basis (see B1 and B2). Selection criteria include researchers at various career stages (from PhD student to Full Professor) and research managers with expertise relevant to the project's objectives, such as technology, politics, and security. The same criteria apply to the selection of focus groups participants, including: researchers from the University of Macerata and associated networks like ERUA dealing with semiconductors and innovation topics; research managers from EARMA and the consortium of the CARDEA project, prioritizing semiconductor-related research profiles; researchers from semiconductor research and innovation ecosystems representing all processes of the semiconductor value chain; R&D managers involved in these processes. The latter two are selected during my placement at INSIDE Industry Association (see B1).

In both the workshops and focus groups, data collection will be limited to basic personal information, i.e., name and surname, email address, age, gender, position and associated entity of the participants. These will be anonymized by applying generic references followed by progressive numbers, i.e., Participant 1, Participant 2, etc., and stored in Zenodo.org., the open repository chosen for research data management.

In the online surveys foreseen in WP2, information will be collected from at least 500 respondents. The same conditions apply for the selection criteria and collection of personal data. To ensure the anonymization of participants, the project will apply generic references followed by progressive numbers, e.g., Researcher 1, Researcher 2, and Research Manager 1, Research Manager 2, etc. With participants' consent, recordings will be collected for research purposes, such as transcription, review, and evaluation.

Recruitment and invitation to participate in the research will be pursued through direct outreach by the researcher, all Supervisors, and all Hosts' research areas via direct email, SMS, phone calls, as well as social media pages in the case of civil society. No risks are foreseen in this phase. If any unexpected complications or results arise, the researcher will promptly address them by consulting with UniMC's ethical advisory board and adapting the methodology to mitigate any issues, ensuring that participants' rights and data are protected. Continuous monitoring and contingency plans are in place to handle any unforeseen ethical concerns or data protection issues. Incentives for participation in the research include providing participants with exclusive access to the research findings and insights, offering certificates of participation, and inviting them to exclusive workshops and conferences for networking opportunities.

Additionally, participants will have the chance to provide feedback on the research process and its outcomes and will be acknowledged for their contributions in the final report and publication. Confidentiality will be maintained in these publications, following the above-mentioned anonymization methods, and personal data protection will be strictly enforced in compliance with GDPR and EU cross-border data flow regulations and guidelines. The researcher will avoid and prevent the collection, storage, sharing, and processing of non-necessary personal data. Data protection is one of the core principles of this research project and will be rigorously enforced.

Ethical issues regarding AI are confined to the use of the ATLAS.ti® in WP1. This software integrates an AI beta tool powered by OpenAI's GPT model, designed to simplify the process of coding literature contents and information for qualitative evaluation, as in the case of this project. Apart from proper and meticulous human agency and oversight on every generated code to comply with the EU "Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI", such a use does not raise any ethical issue.

In conducting research activities at UCB, the researcher will adhere to ethical principles of respect for persons, beneficence, and justice, ensuring informed consent and protecting participant confidentiality. Compliance with local regulations, including the California Consumer Privacy Act (CCPA) and the California Privacy Rights Act (CPRA), will be maintained alongside adherence to federal laws such as the Family Educational Rights and Privacy Act (FERPA), the Common Rule (requiring UC Berkeley's Institutional Review Board (IRB) approval and informed consent) and the Belmont Report. The use of AI will follow principles of transparency, fairness, and accountability, ensuring alignment with and no conflict with EU GDPR and other relevant abovementioned European data protection and ethical standards. In case of pandemic, in order to not pose any health risks to the Fellow, the use of a foreseen project platform will allow constant knowledge sharing and ease workflow among participants, with appropriate initiatives to keep research activity on track (webinars and on-line meetings).

The best standards to grant the safety of the Fellow will be implemented in accordance with the "A Code of Practice for the Safety of Social Researchers". If unforeseen ethical issues arise during research, the Fellow and Supervisors will promptly inform the EU Commission and ensure compliance with ethical principles and applicable international, EU and national law, and the fulfilment of the proper ethical requirements. In addition, copy of the promotional material or information letter and/or invitation to participate in the research involving processing of personal data will be made available.

The opinion of Data Protection Officers (DPO) of UniMC, will be requested. He/she will be involved in all stages of the project, whenever it comes to data privacy issues, since this will help the proposal and grant agreement implementation. The contact details of the DPO will be made available to all data subjects involved in the research.

In addition, UniMC set up a Research Ethics Committee which has the task of expressing opinions, at the request of interested parties, regarding research projects and activities, ensuring that the research complies with the ethical principles deriving from national, European and international legislation. The opinions and approvals of the UniMC DPO concerning the template of the "Information Sheet on Processing and Protection of Data for Participants" and of the "Informed Consent Form" will be obtained. At the time of submission, templates of the information sheet and of the informed consent, specific to this project, are provided below. The final forms will be kept on file and will be submitted later on, if requested by the granting authority.

In order to participate to the planned activities of the project, the enrolled people will be requested to read, confirm the understanding and accept the document "Information Sheet on Processing and Protection of Data for Participants", which will provide clear information concerning:

- a) the purpose of the study, the support of the Programme Horizon Europe of the European Union, the contact details of the scientists responsible for the research;
- b) the details on the procedure that will be followed, how the data will be collected, how data will be anonymized/pseudo-anonymized since the beginning of the

research, how data will be archived, the potential secondary use of the data, confirmation that all data will be treated confidentially (including details on anonymization /pseudonymization), and how to find out about the results of the study;

- c) the rights of the participants in accordance with the GDPR (see Article 12 ff. GDPR), including for the right to refuse to participate and to withdraw their participation, samples or data at any time – without any consequences and the derogations needed to process personal data for research purposes (see Article 89GDPR).

In addition, the participants will be requested to sign an Informed Consent Form. Signing this form, the participants will declare their awareness concerning project details: the researcher responsible for the experiment, the purpose and duration of the experiment, who else is taking part in the study, which procedure will be followed, which data will be collected, how data will be archived, the potential secondary use of the data after finishing the experiment, confirmation that all data will be treated confidentially (including details on anonymization/pseudonymization), and how to find out about the results of the study. Only upon acceptance of the documents described above, any interested person will be involved as project volunteer. Any participant will be able to withdraw from the project at his/her own discretion at any moment in time, without any consequences.

The ethical issues arising from the project's research activities will be addressed in compliance with EU legislation and national laws.

The following legal sources and guidelines are applicable:

European Legislation and Codes:

- The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity Revised Edition, published by ALLEA, All European Academies (2022/23).
- The European Charter for Researchers and relevant legislation of the European Union, including the right to data protection as guaranteed by the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights.
- The Treaty of the European Union (TEU) and the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU), which give effect to the right to privacy by providing individuals with autonomy and control over the way information about them is collected and used (Art. 8).
- The European Convention on Human Rights and other relevant Conventions promoted by the Council of Europe, such as Convention No. 108 on the Protection of Individuals with regard to Automatic Processing of Personal Data (1981).

Data Protection:

- EU Regulation 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, repealing Directive 95/46/EC (GDPR).
- EU Directive 2016/680 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data by competent authorities for the purposes of the prevention, investigation, detection, or prosecution of criminal offences, or the execution of criminal penalties, and on the free movement of such data, repealing Council Framework Decision 2008/977/JHA.

- Handbook on European Data Protection Law (2018 edition).
- European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights and Council of Europe.
- European Court of Human Rights.
- European Data Protection Supervisor.

AI and Research Compliance:

- Artificial Intelligence Act, European Parliament legislative resolution of 13 March 2024 on the proposal for a regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on laying down harmonized rules on Artificial Intelligence (Artificial Intelligence Act) and amending certain Union Legislative Acts (COM(2021)0206–C9-0146/2021–2021/0106(COD)).
- Opinions issued by Advisory Committees of the European Commission, such as the European Group on Ethics in Science and New Technologies, and the European Data Protection Board, as well as case law from the Court of Justice and the European Court of Human Rights, will be considered.

In relation to ethical principles, the researcher is also familiar with and will comply with the main sources of EU and internal law, including:

- The European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR) and its Protocols.
- The UN Declaration of Human Rights.

In this specific research project, the overarching ethical principles apply to:

- Respecting human dignity, welfare, and integrity.
- Ensuring honesty and transparency toward research subjects, notably obtaining free and informed consent (as well as assent whenever relevant).
- Adhering to the data minimization principle, where data may be processed only if it is truly adequate, relevant, and limited to what is necessary for the project.
- Protecting vulnerable persons; ensuring privacy and confidentiality.
- Respecting principles of precaution.
- Promoting justice and inclusiveness.
- Minimizing harm and maximizing benefits.
- Sharing the benefits with disadvantaged populations.
- Respecting and protecting the environment and future generations.

The research activities will be conducted in accordance with fundamental research integrity principles:

- Ensuring reliability in the quality of research, reflected in the design, methodology, analysis, and use of resources.
- Demonstrating honesty in developing, undertaking, reviewing, reporting, and communicating research in a transparent, fair, and unbiased manner.
- Respecting colleagues, research participants, society, ecosystems, cultural heritage, and the environment.

- Being accountable for the research from conception to publication, including its management and organization, as well as for training, supervision, mentoring, and its wider societal impacts.

As the research activities are not covered by the discipline of clinical trials of medicinal products, Beneficiaries and Partner organizations are not subject to the review of ethical committees (see Article 2, par. 2, no. 11 of Regulation (EU) No. 536/2014) nor other kinds of authorizations.

Apart from images, audio, and video recordings in the workshops and focus groups foreseen in WP1 and WP2, the project anticipates no sensitive data collections or the application of intrusive data processing methods, such as profiling, tracking, surveillance, or geo-location tracking.

If ethical issues not foreseen in the project proposal arise during the research activities, the Fellow will promptly inform the EU Commission in order to guarantee the compliance with ethical principles and applicable international, EU, and national law. In any case, the research activities will be carried out in compliance with the ethical code of the University of Macerata:

<https://www.unimc.it/it/ateneo/normativa/regolamenti-di-ateneo/ateneoreg/nuoviregolamentisitoweb.al.06.3.2014/Codice.etico.pdf>.

9. Other issues

Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?

In addition to the data management practices described above, the project will adhere to the University's Policy for Open Access to scientific publications and research data management (<https://www.unimc.it/en/research-bck/research-policy-2/open-science-1/open-access-policy.pdf>) which provides institutional guidelines for managing research outputs and data throughout their lifecycle.

Following this Policy will ensure that project data are managed in accordance with institutional standards and European requirements, in line with Open Science and FAIR principles, throughout the project lifecycle.